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GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER 957781

WP10 – Cooperation & collaboration activities

D10.1 – Report on collaborative activities with similar projects and BRIDGE initiative v1

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Executive Summary

BRIDGE is an important collaboration initiative within Horizon and more specifically high-TRL projects. Attempting to finetune research results and coordinate innovation strategies and frameworks, it manages to extract useful guidelines and contributions to energy system decarbonisation vision of the EU. ACCEPT will actively contribute to BRIDGE initiative and WP10 is dedicated in its larger part to this contribution.

ACCEPT will provide its methodologies and conclusions to the activities of business modelling in BRIDGE and will utilise conclusions on regulatory frameworks and data management. Additionally, the ACCEPT large scale validation testbed -which extends to various cultural, geographical and socioeconomic contexts- will constitute a valuable source of conclusion extraction that ACCEPT will share with other projects.

The project collaborative activities and participation in BRIDGE will be monitored and reported in WP10 and more specifically in T10.1. The present deliverable is the first version out of four in total and includes the planning of relevant activities. Being an introductory deliverable itself, it also includes some generic background on the importance of BRIDGE and intra-project collaboration within Horizon as well as some initial activities already performed in the first semester of ACCEPT.

Chapter 1 of the present document presents the scope and objectives of the task, the deliverable structure as well as its interdependencies with other activity lines of the project.

Chapter 2 includes all the ACCEPT collaboration framework as it has been laid out from the Grant Agreement stage and as it has evolved through the first semester of the project. Within the chapter, the management of BRIDGE participation within the consortium is presented together with the cooperation perspective with other H2020 projects. The main workshops, conferences and events that constitute suitable collaboration platforms are mentioned, such as EUSEW and Sustainable Places, etc.

Chapter 3 summarises the already assumed collaboration activities as conducted within M1-M6, including the BRIDGE General Assembly Meeting, Working Group discussions as well as knowledge sharing platforms established between ACCEPT and other projects of the call LC-SC3-EC-3-2020. A reference to planned activities for the next period is also present.

Finally, **Chapter 4** includes the conclusions in the form of a brief summary of the document.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Scope and Objectives of task

Given the constantly increasing importance of horizontal coordination between H2020 research and innovation projects and the optimal knowledge sharing in the fields of Smart Grid, Energy Storage, Islands, and Digitalisation, BRIDGE initiative will be considered a major part of ACCEPT project. Through the BRIDGE platform, ACCEPT will disseminate interim findings, conclusions and recommendations and at the same time it will analyse the feedback from other projects in order to enrich its knowledge base and spot potential complementarities. Work package 10 is devoted to the planning and monitoring of ACCEPT's participation in BRIDGE initiative as well as the preparation and coordination of synergetic events with "sister" projects.

More specifically, within the frame of task T10.1 active participation in BRIDGE working groups and tasks forces will be accomplished with special focus on prosumer engagement, demand response and energy communities. ACCEPT requires wide feedback in the areas of business modelling and EU regulation frameworks and to this end its participation in the respective working groups is essential. On the other hand, the wide-scale pilot activities in four different countries with numerous engaged users will comprise a significant testbed for framework validation resulting in important conclusions that could provide feedback to BRIDGE task force of energy communities. The above are only some indicative aspects of the ACCEPT project intended interaction within BRIDGE initiative.

Task T10.2 will focus on the preparation, coordination and documentation of collaborative activities with synergetic projects within H2020 frame. Common events and workshops will be coordinated, the results of which will be communicated to BRIDGE initiative but will be also utilized in the frame of dissemination and communication. Given the multitude of the different research and innovation projects, a convenient methodology in order to identify projects with common research grounds is through their corresponding topic IDs of the H2020 work programme. As per the task description, special attention will be given for the establishment of collaboration with project such as DELTA, eDREAM, FLEXCoop, MERLON, WiseGRID, INSULAE, iELECTRIX, PARITY, FLEXIGRID, etc. Different approach will be adopted per project given that some of the abovementioned ones have been recently finalised. The projects that refer to the topic LC-SC3-ES-5-2018-2020 "TSO – DSO – Consumer: Large-scale demonstrations of innovative grid services through demand response, storage and small-scale (RES) generation" will also be examined for synergies. The effort of coordination had already been established prior the start of the project given that the consortia of INTERRFACE & CoordiNet had provided Letters of Intent for ACCEPT.

1.2. Structure of deliverables

Throughout the duration of the project, all activities of WP10 will be documented in four (4) deliverables starting from the present one. The first deliverable D10.1 will identify key subjects for synergies within BRIDGE and will define the basic collaboration roadmap within the project. Each of the following deliverables, namely D10.2, D10.3 and D10.4, will be an advanced version of the previous one reporting all the implemented activities and update the cooperation schedule up to the date of their submission. Table 1 includes an overview of the deliverable together with a brief content description and their submission deadline. The deliverable responsible is the project coordinator (PC) and work package leader (WPL), Hypertech Energy Labs, utilising the essential contribution of the entire consortium in order to be able to exploit all the synergies' potential.

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Table 1 Overview of WP10 deliverable reports

Del. No.	Description	Deadline
D10.1	Report on collaborative activities with similar projects and BRIDGE initiative v1	M6
D10.2	Report on collaborative activities with similar projects and BRIDGE initiative v2	M18
D10.3	Report on collaborative activities with similar projects and BRIDGE initiative v3	M30
D10.4	Report on collaborative activities with similar projects and BRIDGE initiative v4	M42

1.3. Interdependencies with other tasks and deliverables

As described above, WP10 is extended throughout the project lifetime interacting with all involved activities given that it is focused on feedback collection for them and on the export of their findings into collaboration platforms. There is a special link between tasks 10.1 and 10.2 with dissemination work package, namely **WP9 "Outreach activities for impact assessment"**. Actually, the participation in BRIDGE and the establishment of research synergies could be considered a type of dissemination. However, in the ACCEPT project, a distinction has been made between:

1. The dissemination of the results to pilot site stakeholders and the wider communication to the local communities and the
2. The interaction with research peers in terms of experience and knowledge sharing and the creation of strong Research & Innovation synergies

Given the multiple aspects of dissemination and communication, the distinction in the two work packages facilitates the definition of different methodology approaches and adapts the activities accordingly.

Figure 1 ACCEPT Work Package interdependency Graph

Apart from the WP9, the **WP8 “Impact Assessment & Business modelling planning”** is closely linked to WP10 given that the interaction with BRIDGE will give attention to issues related to citizen engagement and energy communities as well as barriers in terms of regulatory/ legislative frameworks and business models. Finally, **WP7 “ACCEPT Demonstration activities”** will be a direct source of findings and conclusions that the consortium of ACCEPT will contribute to BRIDGE elaborations. Figure 1 presents schematically the interdependencies between the different WPs of ACCEPT and the role of WP10 relative to the project elaborations.

1.4. Table of abbreviations

BM	Business Model
CETP	Clean Energy Transition Partnership
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DoA	Description of Action
DR	Demand Response
EGVI	European Green Vehicle Initiative
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IMP	Innovation Management Plan
IoT	Internet of Things
KER	Key Exploitable Results
KoM	Kick-off Meeting
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LEC	Local Energy Community
LL	Living Lab
PC	Project Coordinator
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
RRI	Responsible Research & Innovation
SGAM	Smart Grid Architecture Model
TM	Technical Manager
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WBS	Work Breakdown Structure
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

2. ACCEPT Collaboration framework

2.1. ACCEPT collaboration strategy and synergies within BRIDGE

BRIDGE initiative ranks amongst the most important ones especially for high-TRL H2020 projects in several different fields of Smart Energy Innovation. More specifically, as per the introductory declaration in its website, it constitutes an initiative of the European Commission that attempts to unify the H2020 research projects in Smart Grid and Energy Storage areas in order to build an organized view of horizontal and cross-cutting issues that are creating obstacle towards innovation¹.

The ultimate objective is knowledge sharing between the different activities, exchange of lessons learnt from the different demonstrators deployed in the projects and detection of similarities, overlaps or complementarities in the scientific methodologies. In order to better structure the discussion between the different projects, BRIDGE initiative has launched four (4) different working groups -as described in Figure 2- and three (3) task forces that intersect in between them. Each one represents a discussion group with partners that are participants and others that are responsible to organize the discussions. Some details on the scope of the working groups are mentioned as follows:

Figure 2 BRIDGE working groups. Source: [9]

WG1: Regulation

Regulation is a horizontal issue that is involved in many innovation projects since the smart energy future requires a renovation in the regulatory frameworks of the energy systems. To this end, the discussion focuses on two (2) axes:

- The analysis and promotion of recommendation punch lists on aspects such as the adoption of distributed and utility-scale energy storage. This issue involves several different aspects, such as the asset ownership, the business-market-financial conditions, different technical modalities such as grid characteristics, asset wear and tear, etc.
- The definition of incentives for demand- side management, smart metering and aggregation portfolios.

WG2: Data Management

In the frame of energy system digitalization and taking into account cybersecurity liabilities arising as well as data protection provisions, data management appears to be another significant concept that affects multiple projects. The discussion mainly focuses on:

- The infrastructure issues in communication, the requirements in information exchange, the different use cases with focus on stakeholders, such as the system operators, etc.
- The integrity of data and the privacy preservation for customers.

¹ <https://www.h2020-bridge.eu/>

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- The analytics required for data processing as well as novel data models that cover the new smart DERs interconnected in the system.

WG3: Consumer and citizen engagement

Given that the future energy scenarios involve demand response and locally balanced generation and demand resources, the role of prosumer engagement -both individually and as a member of an energy community- is crucial. Therefore, working group 3 focuses on:

- The creation of a unified consumer engagement approach through the different EU R&I projects.
- The investigation of the optimal approach for motivation of the consumers and the assessment of their active involvement in the energy market.

WG4: Business Models

The energy market is transitioning from a centralised one to an inclusive, multiple-stakeholder marketplace with a wide variety of interactions based on value chains. Thus, the respective working group is required to investigate certain business models and use cases that will combine value propositions and will promote market-based energy transactions. The BM WG has been inactive on 2020 but for 2021 it is considered active

Further to the working groups, BRIDGE internal structure has recently expanded with the addition of "Task Forces" [1] that are dedicated to more specific topics such as:

- Energy Communities
- Scalability and Replicability
- Joint Communication and R&I Priorities, etc.

The tasks forces were introduced in the 2019 BRIDGE General Assembly and intersect with the working groups as shown in Figure 3. Currently some of the task forces are inactive and there is a chance that they might be terminated in due time. This will be updated in the next version of the deliverable.

Footnote: all WGs can contribute to the task forces, especially the one marked with « X » below

BRIDGE – GENERAL ASSEMBLY				
	Working Groups			
	Regulations	Business Models	Data Management	Customer Engagement
Task Forces				
Energy Communities & Self-consumption	X	X	X	X
Replicability & Scalability		X		
Joint Communication				X
Topics / Questions to be addressed by the WGs				
TSO-DSO Cooperation	X		X	
Cybersecurity – Resilience			X	

Figure 3 Overview of BRIDGE WGs & TFs. Source: BRIDGE

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ACCEPT project aspires to actively participate in BRIDGE activities in order to join forces with other H2020 projects and collectively contribute through new findings and demonstrations. From the beginning of the project, an in-depth analysis has been conducted in order to observe the BRIDGE TF/WG to which each activity of the ACCEPT project could contribute. This analysis has been done per each Work Package and for each year of the project in order to better capture the common grounds. The results, based on which the internal allocation regarding BRIDGE participation was conducted, are presented in Figure 4.

WP	BRIDGE Working Groups																BRIDGE Task Forces											
	Data Management				Business Models				Customer Engagement				Regulation				Energy Communities & Self-Consumption				Replicability & Scalability				Joint Communication/ R&I priorities			
	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4
WP1	x	x	x																									
WP2	x				x	x																						
WP3									x	x	x	x					x	x	x	x								
WP4	x	x												x														
WP5		x	x															x	x									
WP8						x	x			x	x		x	x														
WP9															x										x	x	x	x
Lead Partner	Hypertech, IsZEB				RINA-C				GECO				RINA-C				GECO				CIRCE, RINA-C				EEE			

Figure 4 Overlaps of BRIDGE WGs & TFs with ACCEPT research activities.

ACCEPT is in the process of creating a wide spread validation framework including four (4) pilot sites that are or aspire to become energy communities. Each pilot will engage numerous prosumers and business stakeholders in Demand Response practices and the project elaborations will focus on consumer engagement analysis, community mapping and Living Lab set-up in pilot sites. Through this process **ACCEPT will utilise feedback and best practices provided by BRIDGE Task Force on Energy Communities & Customer Engagement Working Group. In parallel, it will provide these bodies with findings and conclusions created through the course of the project activities.**

ACCEPT framework also includes real-time data collection as well as processing and curation of operational data of residences through IoT solutions. Specific tasks are dedicated to the creation of a Security Access Control framework for minimisation of security and privacy risks that facilitates bi-directional information flow. Based on these facts, **the active participation of ACCEPT project in BRIDGE Data Management Working Group is considered to be of strategic importance.**

Last but not least, the construct of Energy Communities is quite new which implies the need for elaboration on innovative business models that are prosumer-centric and offer compound Demand Response (DR) services. To this end, **the re-organisation of the BRIDGE Business Models Working Group is considered to be of strategic importance for ACCEPT** and that is the reason why the project will support it.

Overall, ACCEPT project intends to be in continuous interaction within but also beyond BRIDGE initiative with projects that focus on the same of neighbouring scientific fields. Therefore, it intends to create a

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high-level roadmap of activities that could reinforce the collaboration between projects, strengthen R&I synergies in order to enhance the quality of research outcomes.

2.1.1. Management of BRIDGE participation within the consortium

Based on the preliminary analysis of common grounds between the project activities and the BRIDGE focus groups, as presented in Figure 4, an internal allocation has been conducted so that ACCEPT follows-up all the Working Groups and Task Forces. Several members of the consortium will also attend (Hypertech, CIRCE, CERTH, RINA-C, GECO) in the General Assembly with the coordinator having the responsibility of project representation. Table 2 includes the lead partners that have been allocated to the different BRIDGE Working Groups and Task Forces at the project Kick-off Meeting (KoM).

Table 2 Lead partners of ACCEPT project per BRIDGE WG & TF

BRIDGE bodies	Lead Partner	Contact Details of Responsible Person
Working Groups		
Data Management	Hypertech IsZEB	d.tsagkrasoulis@hypertech.gr s.tseranidis@iszeb.gr
Business Models	RINA-C	alessandra.cuneo@rina.org
Customer Engagement	GECO	bonnie.murphy@geco-global.com
Regulation	RINA-C	alessandra.cuneo@rina.org
BRIDGE Task Forces		
Energy Communities & Self-Consumption	GECO	bonnie.murphy@geco-global.com
Replicability & Scalability	CIRCE, RINA-C	dmrivas@fcirce.es alessandra.cuneo@rina.org
Joint Communication/ R&I priorities	EEE	s.Koch@eee-info.net

Beyond the plain participation in BRIDGE WGs and TFs, ACCEPT project has a strategic intention to be more involved in the organisation of the activities and the finetuning of the collective conclusions at BRIDGE level. Therefore, one of the ACCEPT consortium major partners, **RINA-C**, has offered to co-chair the **Business Model Working Group**, and **Hypertech Energy Labs**, the project coordinator, has offered to be an “Active Contributor” in the **Data Management Working Group**.

2.1.2. H2020 projects with strong collaboration perspective

Both within the frame of BRIDGE and beyond it, ACCEPT has launched an initial research of similar H2020 projects based on their corresponding topics and calls. Based on the Description of Action (DoA) provisions, the investigation initiated with topic ID **LC-SC3-ES-5-2018-2020** “TSO – DSO – Consumer: Large-scale demonstrations of innovative grid services through demand response, storage and small-scale (RES) generation”. Table 3 below provides an overview of this investigation effort.

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Table 3 Summary overview of H2020 projects linked to the topic LC-SC3-ES-5-2018-2020

Acronym	Title	Scope	Start date	End date
CREATORS	CREATIng cOmmunity eneRgy Systems	Support of technical, financial & social processes in Community Energy Systems (CES) in order to facilitate local stakeholders. The objective is to provide local CES agents with the capacity for high-quality simulation, etc.	1/9/2020	31/10/2023
ROBINSON	Smart integRation Of local energy sources and innovative storage for flexiBle, secure and cost-efficient eNergy Supply ON industrialized islands	Usage optimisation of local RES through the deployment of an integrated, smart and cost-efficient energy system coupling thermal and electrical networks, demonstrated in industrial environment in Norway.	1/10/2020	30/9/2024
REDREAM	REAL CONSUMER ENGAGEMENT THROUGH A NEW USER-CENTRIC ECOSYSTEM DEVELOPMENT FOR END-USERS ASSETS IN A MULTI-MARKET SCENARIO	The projects aims to facilitate the participation of the prosumers in the energy market, based on an innovative Service Dominant Logic example.	1/10/2020	30/9/2023
MAESHA	deMOnstration of smArt and flExible solutions for a decarboniSed energy future in Mayotte and other European isLands	The project aims to develop the required system flexibility, storage and energy management solutions to permit large-scale integration of RES.	1/11/2020	31/10/2024
IANOS	IntegrAted SolutioNs for the DecarbOnization and Smartification of Islands	The project is based on 2 Lighthouse islands (Terceira-PT, Ameland-NL) & 3 Fellow islands (FI) (Lampedusa-IT, Bora-Bora-FR, Nisyros-GR) in order to realise their joint decarbonisation and energy adequacy vision.	1/10/2020	30/9/2024

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LocalRES	Empowering local renewable energy communities for the decarbonisation of the energy systems	The project develops a digital tool suite that enables social welfare through the energy community construct and with RES transformation.	1/5/2021	30/4/2025
eNeuron	greEN Energy hUBs for local integRATED energy cOMMUNITIES optimization	The project creates an innovative tool suite optimised operational aspects within local energy communities (LECs) with large-scale penetration of DERs and multi-scale energy network coupling.	1/11/2020	31/10/2024
VPP4ISLANDS	Virtual Power Plant for Interoperable and Smart isLANDS	The project objective is the enabling of RES integration, the fast-paced transformation to sustainable and digitalised energy systems in Islands through storage and consumer engagement.	1/10/2020	31/3/2024
REnergetic	Community-empowered Sustainable Multi-Vector Energy Islands	The project aspires to enable islanded energy systems or weak grids and non-interconnected systems to accommodate large shares of locally produced RES and comply with the Clean Energy Package provisions.	1/11/2020	30/4/2024
OneNet	One Network for Europe	The project attempts to facilitate a unified energy system across the EU which is concurrently based on decentralised production and distributed flexibility exploitation.	1/10/2020	30/9/2023
TwinERGY	Intelligent interconnection of prosumers in positive energy communities with twins of things for digital energy markets	The project develops a Digital Twin that optimises demand-side management while preserving the well-being of prosumers and their activity patterns and day-to-day operations.	1/11/2020	31/10/2023

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TIGON	Towards Intelligent DC-based hybrid Grids Optimizing the network performance	The project focuses on new generation DC or hybrid grid paradigm that offers better potential to accommodate RES and other DC loads connected to energy storage and EVs.	1/9/2020	31/8/2024
BRIGHT	Boosting DR through increased community-level consumer engagement by combining Data-driven and blockChain technology Tools with social science approaches and multi-value service design	The project targets the energy community-based development of demand-side response through newly introduced technologies in the energy field, such as blockchain platforms, etc.	1/11/2020	31/10/2023
SERENE	Sustainable and Integrated Energy Systems in Local Communities	The project objective comprises the development and demonstration of energy community solutions that are integrated, digitalised and sustainable.	1/5/2021	30/4/2025
iFLEX	Intelligent Assistants for Flexibility Management	The project targets prosumer empowerment and facilitation of the participation in DR transactions through a SW agent, the so-called “iFLEX Assistant” that connects consumers with energy system.	1/11/2020	31/10/2023
SENDER	Sustainable Consumer engagement and demand response	The project focuses on next-generation DR and home-automation solutions that will facilitate a consumer-centric transformation of the energy markets. In parallel consumer engagement through co-creation methodologies is applied.	1/10/2020	30/9/2024
ISLANDER	Accelerating the decarbonisation of island energy systems	Showcasing the island of Borkum, the project attempts to develop efficient and holistic solutions in order to enable the effective	1/10/2020	30/9/2024

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		integration of RES in islanded parts of the energy system.		
HYPERRIDE	Hybrid Provision of Energy based on Reliability and Resiliency by Integration of DC Equipment	The project focus on innovative DC and hybrid energy grids contributing in the development and implementation of such solutions.	1/10/2020	30/9/2024
HESTIA	Holistic dEmand response Services for European residentIAI communities	The project aspires to provide compound services (energy & non-energy) in terms of an innovative demand response framework and with a concurrent holistic approach combining decentralised generation and demand on local level.	1/11/2020	31/10/2023
RESPONSE	integRatEd Solutions for POsitive eNErgy and reSilient CitiEs	The project aims to provide positive energy to energy districts based on innovative solution demonstrators in 2 Lighthouse cities 6 Fellow cities.	1/10/2020	30/9/2025
ALIGHT	Copenhagen Airport: a Lighthouse for the introduction of sustainable aviation solutions for the future	The attempts to contribute to the global requirements of greenhouse gas (GHG) emission reduction. The project demonstrations will comprise two sustainability solutions.	1/11/2020	31/10/2024

2.1.3. Regular events to be used as collaboration platforms

ACCEPT will utilise all the already established platforms for networking and feedback exchange among different R&I projects and invested stakeholders. Such platforms are offered through signature events, such as EUSEW, Enlit, Sustainable Places, etc. Following a short overview of these platforms in Table 4.

Table 4 Major established collaboration platforms considered by ACCEPT

<p>25-29 OCTOBER 2021 EU SUSTAINABLE ENERGY WEEK TOWARDS 2030: RESHAPING THE EUROPEAN ENERGY SYSTEM</p> <p>#EUSEW2021</p>	<p>European Sustainability Energy Week constitutes a Policy Conference focused on RES and the concept of Energy Efficiency. It is organised and coordinated by the European Commission aiming to pave the way towards 2030 and 2050 visions of energy system decarbonisation.</p>
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	<p>It represents a highly inclusive platform that attempts to gather R&I projects together with invested stakeholders in order to make elaborations in sustainability and respective policy frameworks that can foster it.</p> <p>The event includes different platforms, such as:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. Networking Village ii. Energy Fair iii. Energy Lab iv. Energy Talks <p>Which offer networking opportunities and forge collaborations.</p>
	<p>Enlit is one of the largest exhibitions within the EU and globally that focuses on Smart Energy Innovation, Utilities and Power Generation. It accommodates a multitude of events, focus groups and fairs that connect the stakeholder community and provide a platform where industry meets research and innovation. The ultimate target is to foster all aspects to a sound transition towards a new sustainable energy landscape.</p>
	<p>Sustainable Places annual conference constitutes a platform that attempts to showcase the most significant results from H2020 projects in the research areas of building automation, sustainable urban design, utilities and energy industry. Given the wide participation of R&I projects, the event offers a unique collaboration and feedback exchange platform.</p>

Apart from the already established platforms, ACCEPT has joined forces with some of the projects that were shortlisted in Table 3, in order to create an addition collaboration platform. The projects were selected based on their similarities and the scientific common grounds and an overview of them is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5 H2020 project collaboration platform co-organised by ACCEPT

The joined platform aspires to conduct a meticulous work during the projects' lifetime in order to ensure collaboration at multiple levels, e.g. requirements, deployment, impact assessment, conclusions, etc. The main structure of the platform will include the following aspects:

- i. A pool /repository of common material of the H2020 projects including the focus areas of national legislation / regulatory frameworks on energy communities, market codes/regulations and good practices on stakeholder engagement.
- ii. The co-organisation of key dissemination workshops on annual basis in the frame of conference platforms such as the Sustainable Places.
- iii. Systematic work on finetuning and homogenisation of the business and use cases of the various project, where applicable, in order to ensure compatibility and easy comparability of project outcomes, impact assessment methodologies, etc.
- iv. Regular, thematic meetings between the projects during the different research phases.

2.2. Internal reporting and evaluation of collaboration activities

Given that there are multiple collaboration attempts carried out by the coordinator and by several other consortium members, there is a need to establish an internal reporting process in order to summarise the results, communicate them internally to the consortium but also report them in the regular technical project management reports.

In terms of internal management of ACCEPT participation in BRIDGE, Hypertech Energy Labs, as the coordinator and leader of WP10, will have a horizontal and supervisory role. Therefore, the partner should be included in all the communications with BRIDGE.

When the project is requested to provide a task-specific feedback to BRIDGE or fill-in a specific survey/questionnaire, the following partners should be involved:

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- i. The assigned WG-TF member from ACCEPT
- ii. HYPERTECH as the leader of BRIDGE activities.
- iii. In case that the results of an ACCEPT deliverable need to be shared, the leader of the respective task should also be involved.

Finally, any activity within BRIDGE (meetings, material, etc.) should be communicated to EEE and disseminated. In order to facilitate internal communication, a special mailing list has been created under the e-mail address: wp10-bridge@accept-project.eu.

3. Report of ACCEPT Collaboration Activities

3.1. BRIDGE collaboration activities M1-M6

Within the first six months of the project, ACCEPT has participated in the annual BRIDGE procedure and in addition to this the consortium has attended most of the meetings including both the General Assembly and the thematic discussions. Further details on the events as well as the project's participation and contribution are provided below.

3.1.1. BRIDGE General Assembly Meeting (March 2-4)

The annual BRIDGE General Assembly Meeting for 2021 took place during three days between the 2nd and the 4th of March. The meeting brought together multiple partners from different European research projects on the fields of Smart Grid, Energy Storage and Islands & Digitalization.

As of the time of the meeting, BRIDGE comprised 59 ongoing research projects. Of those projects, 23 were newly introduced to BRIDGE and participated in the General Assembly for the first time. ACCEPT was among those projects and an introductory presentation regarding ACCEPT and its goals was delivered during the meeting (please see the presentation herein, **Annex 1**). The rest of the newly introduced research projects were: BRIGHT, CREATORS, ENEURON, FLEXIGRID (863876), FLEXPLAN, HESTIA, HYPERRIDE, IANOS, IFLEX, RENERGETIC, ROBINSON, SENDER, TIGON, TWINERGY, VPP4ISLANDS, BD4NRG, ISLANDER, MAESHA, MAGNITUDE, ONENET and REDREAM.

Furthermore, there were presentations from three projects which ended during the last year which highlighted the projects' key results and findings. Those projects were: INTEGRID, CRYOHUB and TDX-ASSIST.

Among the presentations during the General Assembly Meeting were a presentation of the Clean Energy Transition Partnership (CETP), a presentation by EGVI (European Green Vehicle Initiative) titled "2Zero: Towards Zero Emission Road Transport. An overview of the partnership" as well presentations on Smart Networks for Energy Transition (by ETIP) and on Low TRL Projects.

More than 200 participants have participated in the plenary session of the BRIDGE GA 2021 and around 70 participants at each of the parallel sessions. The sessions covered the work the BRIDGE working groups on Data Management, Regulation, Consumer and Citizen Engagement and Business models as well as its Task Force. The details of the agenda of the event can be seen in Figure 6.

Structure of the agenda

DAY 1: 02/03/2021	09:00 – 13:00	PLENARY 1		
	14:00 – 16:00	Parallel session 2.1 - DATA MANAGEMENT WG 1/2 -		
DAY 2: 03/03/2021	09:00 – 10:30	Focus Topic – EV ENERGY FLEXIBILITY –		
	10:30 – 10:45	Coffee Break		
	10:45 – 13:00	Parallel session 1 REGULATION WG	Parallel session 2.2 DATA MANAGEMENT WG 2/2	Parallel session 3 CONSUMER AND CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT WG
	13:00 – 14:00	Lunch Break		
	14:00 – 16:00	Parallel session 4 UNLOCKING THE POTENTIAL OF EU ISLANDS TO BECOME THE LOCOMOTIVES OF EUROPEAN ENERGY TRANSITION	Parallel session 5 INNOVATION AND APPLICATION OF DIRECT CURRENT TECHNOLOGIES	Parallel session 6 BUSINESS MODELS
	16:30-17:30	NETWORKING EVENT ORGANISED BY MUSE GRIDS PROJECT		
DAY 3: 04/03/2021	09:00 – 12:30	PLENARY 2		

Figure 6 Agenda of the BRIDGE GA 2021. Source: BRIDGE GA 2021 - Final Agenda.docx

The ACCEPT project introduction during the morning session is also shown in Figure 7.

Day 1 Morning: Plenary (2nd March)

9:00 – 9:20	Welcome & Introduction – Vincent Berrutto Head of Unit DG ENER Innovation, Research, Digitalisation, Competitiveness	
9:20 – 9:30	Presentation of the agenda and Horizon Europe - Cristobal Irazoqui Policy Officer DG ENER Innovation, Research, Digitalisation, Competitiveness	
09:30 – 10:30	Plenary 1.1: Presentation of 2020 actions by Working Groups WG Regulation, WG Data Management & WG Consumer and Citizen Engagement	
10:30 – 10:45	Coffee Break	
10:45 – 11:15	Plenary 1.2: Presentation of 2020 actions by Task Forces TF R&I priorities, TF Replicability and Scalability & TF Energy communities and self consumption	
	Plenary 2: New BRIDGE Projects – Part 1 10 new projects pitching. Each project will address 2 issues: 1) Intro & objectives of the project 2) Identification of areas that match the current work in BRIDGE	
11:15 – 12:00	ACCEPT – 3min	Vasiliki Katsiki
	BRIGHT – 3min	Massimo Bertoncini
	CREATORS – 3min	Christof De Knop
	eNeuron – 3min	Marialaura Di Somma
	FLEXIGRID (863876) – 3 min	Manos Varvagiros
	FlexPlan – 3min	Gianluigi Migliavacca
	HESTIA – 3min	Andrea Martinez
	Hyperride – 3min	Gerhard Jambrich
	Ianos – 3min	Nuno Marinho
	IFLEX– 3min	Markus Taumberger

Figure 7 Agenda of the morning session day 1 – the plenary session on 2nd March 2021. Source: BRIDGE GA 2021 - Final Agenda.docx

The key takeaways of the 2021 BRIDGE General Assembly are also summarized in the BRIDGE website links below:

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- BRIDGE General Assembly 2021 Key Takeaways:
<https://www.h2020-bridge.eu/bridge-general-assembly-2021-key-takeaways/>
- BRIDGE General Assembly 2021 Key Takeaways.PDF:
<https://www.h2020-bridge.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/BRIDGE-GA-2021-Final-Conclusions.pdf>

In the frame of the General Assembly, several thematic sessions were held that ACCEPT took the chance to participate. Indicatively, within the parallel session 6 on “Business models”, Alessandra Cuneo (RINA-C) along with partners from GECCO, presented the intention of ACCEPT to follow on business models analysis and the innovative approach based on use value network approaches to business modelling (e.g. Service-dominant business model radar). The presentation introduced the project, the pilot sites, the open innovation approach to product and service development as well as the value network perspective on business design. It is also included in the present document in **Annex 1**.

On day 2, GECCO actively participated in the parallel session 3 “Consumer and citizen engagement” and joined the subgroup “Socio economic drivers of engagement”.

The BRIDGE representatives of Hypertech Energy Labs, CERTH and EEE participated in the in the plenary sessions as well as in the parallel sessions.

Sessions attended - Day 1 – 2nd March:

- Plenary 1.1: Presentation of 2020 actions by Working Groups
- Plenary 1.2: Presentation of 2020 actions by Task Forces
- Plenary 2: New BRIDGE Projects – Part 1
- Parallel session 2.1: Data Management
- Plenary 3: New BRIDGE Projects – Part 2
- Plenary 4: Presentation of the Clean Energy Transition Partnership CETP

Sessions attended - Day 2 - 3rd March:

- Parallel session 2.2: Data Management
- Parallel session 3 Consumer and Citizen engagement
- Parallel session 6 Business models

Sessions attended - Day 3 - 4th March:

- Plenary 5: New BRIDGE Projects
- Plenary 6: Ended BRIDGE Projects
- Plenary 7: ETIP Smart Networks for Energy Transition
- Plenary 8: Low TRL projects cluster
- Plenary 9: Joint communication
- Plenary 10: Outcome of the discussions on the parallel sessions

More details will also be provided in the following paragraph, which brief the generic contribution of ACCEPT to BRIDGE WGs and TFs.

3.1.2. Activities and participation within BRIDGE Working Groups and Task Forces

EEE is dedicated to represent the ACCEPT project in the Task Force “Joint Communication” and therefore the participation on plenary 9 of day 3 of the event was especially important to hear about how this Task Force is organized, what they have achieved during the last year and how they intend to proceed with their activities.

DATA MANAGEMENT WG

The participation of ACCEPT project in the elaborations of the Data Management Working Group kick started from the 2021 BRIDGE General Assembly (2-4 March 2021). During the meeting, several discussions were held on the topic of standardization efforts and the ways by which BRIDGE can contribute to those efforts and the development of standards and a common approach for research in the fields of Smart Grid, Energy Storage and Islands & Digitalization. As a first step, a common BRIDGE repository for use cases was created and presented on the General Assembly by BRIDGE stakeholders. The repository hosts use cases of Smart-Grid projects based on a common template by the IEC 62559-2 standard titled “Use case methodology – Part 2: Definition of the templates for use cases, actor list and requirements list” [2]. Each use case is logged on the repository on the standardized template and includes information such as a description of the use case, the different roles involved as well as descriptions of the solutions, standards and KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) used among other information. The repository is currently active and research projects can contribute their use cases to it as well as view the use cases of other similar projects which are uploaded on the repository. This allows a common approach between different projects to materialize through the sharing of data and information. The use case repository is currently active on the following link as shared by BRIDGE: <https://smart-grid-use-cases.github.io/>.

The summary of the repository, its utility and function were presented and discussed among ACCEPT partners during the ACCEPT Plenary Teleconference of 8th April 2021 and the relevant information and links subsequently circulated in the minutes in order for ACCEPT to participate in the initiative with its use cases as well as to learn from the other projects’ use cases and align its path accordingly.

REGULATION WG

During the General Assembly a session was dedicated to the Regulation WG. The chairs of the Regulation WG presented the results achieved in 2020 based on 1) The Harmonized Electricity Role Model, 2) The Demo ID-Cards, 3) Products, services, coordination models and market design. A discussion was held to understand which topics could be analysed for 2021. A survey was conducted by the Chairs with the WG members on 24th March to understand interesting topics from the projects.

The official KOM of the Regulation WG has been held on 16th June where Alessandra Cuneo (RINA-C) joined on behalf of ACCEPT project. During the meeting the tracks and the topics to be discussed during 2021 has been shared by the WG chair leaders.

In agreement with Hypertech as Coordinator, it has been decided that ACCEPT project, through the active participation of RINA-C, will contribute for 2021 to Action 2 focusing on: 1) Service provision by energy communities, ii) service provision by e-mobility and iii) market incentives to support consumer engagement.

BUSINESS MODELS WG

The business models WG has been re-activated in 2021. During the General Assembly several new projects presented innovative approaches for business models related to Demand Response (DR) and DR aggregation, as well as Local energy markets and prosumers. During the discussion several ideas to focus on in the BM WG has been identified.

Following the General Assembly, the Business Innovation Manager of ACCEPT, Alessandra Cuneo (RINA-C), has been contacted by BRIDGE to support the leadership of the WG. Several calls have been organized by BRIDGE Secretariat together with the Chairmanship (Andrej Gubina (Chair), Alessandra Cuneo (RINA-C, co-chair)) and representatives from the EC to identify the topics for 2021. The kick-off of the WG is planned early of July.

CONSUMER AND CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT WG

ACCEPT, through its Living Lab Manager GECCO Global, is actively represented in activities and knowledge exchange between the different members of the “Consumer and citizen engagement” working group and in particular of the subgroup “Socio economic drivers of engagement”. The first working group meeting was conducted in 15th April.

REPLICABILITY & SCALABILITY TF

CIRCE has been involved in the Replicability & Scalability Task Force, specifically in the subgroup focused on the development of the Subroutine 3 since the second semester of 2020 until M3 of ACCEPT project. Although the core of the work was developed in 2020, the last closing remarks and final editing of the 2nd version of “Guidelines for implementing the prescribed methodology-Additional Subroutines and requirements” were done during the period comprising M1 and M3 of ACCEPT project.

The subroutine in which CIRCE is involved aims at establishing generic and quantifiable KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) based on the KERs (Key Exploitable Results) identified in the previous subroutine, that can track the results of these KERs as the project progresses. The challenge faced in this subroutine was to start from KERs which are project specific and develop generic KPIs, which are universal and not project specific. Among the current 64 projects that are part of the BRIDGE initiative, 35 had already published their KPIs (or had a list of KPIs ready to be published). From that specific selection CIRCE analysed the KPIs of 9 BRIDGE projects (FLEXICIENCY, FLEXIGRID, IELECTRIX, NOBEL GRID, OSMOSE, P2P SMARTEST, InteGrid, INSULAE and TILOS) matching those with the KERs of the specific project classifying them according to the following attributes (ref. to Figure 8).

Figure 8 Classification Attributes for KPIs

Last step of the subroutine was to apply the methodology to a subset of selected projects that were enough detailed information regarding KERs was obtained in the previous subroutine 2. The contribution from CIRCE in this last step was minor.

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The work that is scheduled to be the subject of the last phase of the Replicability and Scalability Task Force is based on the following axes:

- Use case technology solutions for developing the smart system of 2030 / 2050 mapped in the SGAM architecture [3]. This library of use cases should continuously grow to facilitate the solution adaption of project consortia in mapping their planned project objectives and maximising the benefits of the SGAM process. This repository will contain the adapted mapping together with a detailed description of the use case and what makes it different from other related use cases that have been archived in the repository. An attempt will be made to adapt a coding system that will help to manage the repository with an effective query application based on an effective taxonomy.
- The family of solutions provided through the adapted use cases will be exhaustively linked to approved standards and codes provided by the appropriate EU bodies: CEN, CENELEC, ETSI, ENTSO-E etc.

The kick-off meeting for the 2021 activities in this Task Force was held in 17th of May.

3.1.3. Projects collaboration under the call: LC-SC3-EC-3-2020 - Consumer engagement and demand response

In the frame of the horizontal collaboration between H2020 projects -beyond BRIDGE initiative-, the five H2020 presented in Figure 5 have attempted to create a unified knowledge sharing, cocreation and feedback exchange platform. In order to kick-off this activity, a teleconference took place with the following agenda:

- i. Project presentations describing their status, short-term goals and pilot sites' situation.
- ii. Current status in the area of user engagement sharing the identified problems and potential solutions.
- iii. Future challenges (e.g., the maintenance of user engagement) and mitigation actions.
- iv. Open discussion including comments and any other business.

The goal of the meeting is to create a list of risks/problems and contingency actions to implement and to schedule **thematic meetings** aiming to understand how projects are tackling certain common issues and try to replicate successful actions in other projects. The projects discussed the main challenges that they have identified so far. These are summarised in the schematic of Figure 9.

ACCEPT

When and how to engage the users?

iFLEX

How to keep users motivated to use iFLEX?

HESTIA

What could be the form of co-creation of the DR platform and user recruitment during a pandemic?

SENDER

How to address the challenge to mix users and technical developers in a co-creation steering group?

Figure 9 Challenges presented by the projects in the first thematic meeting

The outcome of the meeting included a series of actions that each project committed to implement. More specifically:

- ACCEPT has planned to work on the use cases from early stages and create relevant material before going live. In parallel, the situation in the pilot sites is being monitored in terms of Covid-19 restrictions.
- I-FLEX is investigating the kind of incentives, such as monetary, vouchers, lotteries etc., to use in order to engage the users.
- HESTIA is in the process of creating a short video in the languages of the pilots in order to introduce the project to the local communities. Surveys are also being prepared in the local languages. As a start of the pilot activities, short online interactions with a few households, namely five (5) in each pilot, are being arranged. Finally, there is a plan to recruit and engage “pilot ambassadors” to be advocates for the project.
- REDREAM has decided to initially focus on the local recruitment through the webpage.
- SENDER intends to introduce technical stakeholders and simple users into a common cocreation framework and in parallel work on the use cases to be demonstrated.

Microsoft Teams will be used as a permanent data repository supporting the knowledge sharing process between the projects. Being a horizontal major concern, user engagement will be in the focus of inter-project discussions with the ACCEPT partners contributing with the extensive analysis of WP3 and the iFLEX partners through their “User Engagement and co-creation framework”. Issues such as the “virtual” community engagement during the pandemic period and the balancing of user recruitment with GDPR provisions will be addressed.

3.2. Planned collaboration activities for the next period

The next steps of ACCEPT with regards to the BRIDGE initiative comprise the regular participation in all WGs and TFs either through answering surveys, provision of written contribution or participation in meetings. As mentioned above, the participation in the Business model WG will be even deeper since the Business Innovation Manager of ACCEPT will assume one of the leadership roles. In parallel, ACCEPT aspires to also participate in the General Assembly body of BRIDGE and contribute to material such as the BRIDGE newsletter, brochure, etc.

Concerning the collaboration with similar H2020 projects, ACCEPT intends to continue supporting the “thematic meetings” with HESTIA-iFLEX-REDREAM-SENDER. The identified next step list of the newly founded “consortium of projects” includes the following milestones:

1. Potential follow-up call on user engagement.
2. Preparation of 1-pager with reporting elements of each project including its current status and 6-month ahead plan.
3. Public and approved deliverable sharing.
4. Set-up of Microsoft Teams environment for the collaboration management.
5. Organise a common workshop on energy communities and demand response which will be potentially hosted in the upcoming Sustainable Places 2021 conference (29 Sept-1 Oct).
6. Participation in LinkedIn group [4] on Demand Response for networking purposes.

4. Conclusions

BRIDGE constitutes an initiative of utmost importance for research and innovation Horizon projects attempting to harmonise their results, coordinate inputs and outputs in order to produce useful conclusions that contribute to the realisation of the roadmap towards the transition to a sustainable energy landscape with Smart Grids, Renewable Energy Sources and Energy Storage.

ACCEPT intends to actively participate in BRIDGE structure and contribute with its tools, methodologies and pilot testbeds to overcome cross-cutting issues that constitute obstacles towards innovation. Given the project objectives and challenges, it seems essential to utilise BRIDGE feedback on business modelling and EU regulation. On the other hand, given the project's wide demand response pilot validation framework including different cultural, geographical and socioeconomic contexts, it can provide valuable feedback to BRIDGE elaboration. This "win-win" relationship between BRIDGE and ACCEPT project will be explored in WP10 and more specifically in T10.1.

The collaboration strategy of the project is defined and presented herein, in D10.1 which is the first deliverable of WP10. It was important for the project to construct its collaboration roadmap from scratch in order to have the time capacity to organise synergies throughout the different phases of the project, from the requirements-architecture to the pilot roll-out and validation. Based on the DoA provisions [5], the activities regarding BRIDGE and wider collaboration attempts will be documented in the deliverables D10.2, D10.3 and D10.4.

Besides the participation in the BRIDGE activities, that have already started with the General Assembly of March, the WG & TF discussions and the contribution to the brochure of 2021, ACCEPT has also initiated a horizontal project collaboration along with HESTIA-iFLEX-REDREAM-SENDER. This permanent project platform includes the creation of a common e-repository to be utilised as knowledge hub and means of feedback exchange as well as the arrangement of joint dissemination and communication events utilising renowned and well-established platforms, such as EUSEW, Sustainable Places, Enlit, etc. Finally, all projects decided to arrange a series of "thematic meetings" in order to discuss their different approaches and methodologies, to harmonise their views and jointly elaborate on outcomes.

In the terms of next steps, ACCEPT intends to follow-up all WGs, TFs and General Assemblies of BRIDGE and contribute to any surveys or reports required. The project will also support the joint collaboration platform that has been created by the five Demand Response & Energy Community-related H2020 projects.

Through its meticulous and well-defined research methodology but also through its open and collaborative approach, ACCEPT attempts to widely communicate its innovative framework and maximise its impact in the pilot sites and among the various stakeholder groups.

5. References

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Annex 1

Vasiliki Katsiki
Project Coordinator

BRIDGE General Assembly 2nd, 3rd and 4th March 2021

These initiatives are funded by

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ACCEPT– Intro & Objectives

ACCEPT project investigates demand flexibility potential in the frame of energy communities. An innovative framework will be created and validated around demand response and aggregated flexibility optimization from diverse distributed generation-demand-storage assets.

ACCEPT project objectives include:

- The delivery of ACCEPT Digital Toolbox that
 - enables the **delivery of compound DR services** to community members and
 - optimizes the **aggregated flexibility potential** at district-level for the formulation of **community-based VPPs** that can participate in energy markets
- The definition of best practices on prosumer engagement and the stipulation of a concrete methodology that evaluates prosumer acceptability and benefits from Energy Community schemes.
- The development of **energy community governance tools**
- The creation of value propositions for a set of **intra-community service offerings**
- The creation of **business models on different roles** that an energy community can assume **in the energy markets**

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ACCEPT– Synergies & contribution to BRIDGE

- BRIDGE Task Force on Energy Communities & Customer Engagement Working Group:
 - i. Validation in 4 pilot sites that already are or aspire to become energy communities.
 - ii. Wide participation in Demand Response activities per pilot site – primarily prosumers but also business stakeholders.
 - iii. Significant attention on consumer engagement analysis, community mapping and Living Lab set-up in pilot sites.
- BRIDGE Data Management Working Group:
 - i. Real-time collection, (pre)processing and curation of operational data of residences through IoT solutions
 - ii. Bi-directional information flow under a Security Access Control framework for minimisation of security and privacy risks.
- BRIDGE Business Models Working Group:
 - i. Innovative BM elaboration on community roles in the Energy System
 - ii. Synthesis of consumer-centric compound DR services

*ACCEPT can utilise valuable feedback and provide its contribution to
EC TF, CE –DM-BM WGs of BRIDGE*

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User Engagement
26/05/2021

Grant Number	957781
Call	H2020-LC-SC3-2020-EC-ES-SCC Topic: LC-SC3-EC-3-2020 - Consumer engagement and demand response
Duration	42 months. Start Date: 1-1-2021
Total EU contribution	€ 5,862,476.38
Partners	16 Project Partners Coordinator: HYPERTECH Partners: CIRCE, GECO, QUE, CERTH, Witside, UCC, RINA-C, Mytilineos, ESB, EDBR, MIWenergia, LaSolar, AEM, Viesgo, EEE
Pilots	Demonstration Sites: GR: Aspra Spitia Community in Viotia - Mytilineos ES: Renewable Energy Cooperative Buildings, Murcia - LaSolar NL: Eva Lanxmeer Community - Culemborg - EDBR/ ESB CH: Motta Massagno District - Lugano - AEM Pre-Validation testbeds: GR: nZEB - DIH Testbed Facility Thessaloniki - CERTH GR: Hypertech Office & HEL Smart Homes Athens -Hypertech ES: Historical consumption data Spain - Viesgo

2

ACCEPT project investigates demand flexibility potential in the frame of energy communities. An innovative framework will be created and validated around demand response and aggregated flexibility optimization from diverse distributed generation-demand-storage assets.

ACCEPT project objectives include:

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- The creation of value propositions for a set of **intra-community service offerings**
- The creation of **business models on different roles** that an energy community can assume **in the energy markets**

3

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Current Status

- Preparation of Living Lab material
- B2C surveys - gather early feedback on Use Cases
- Organisation of user engagement workshops (due in June and July)

Challenges (current and future)	Solutions
COVID crisis (elephant in the room!)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitor local situation / measures • Go virtual
Timeline - when do I engage?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build a time plan -key updates/user inputs, build contingency, minimise inconvenience • What are the pre-requisites
Approach - how do I engage?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consult pilot partners (energy community reps) - they know! • Experience from other similar projects • Understand circumstances
Make engagement material relevant, comprehensive, relatable, interesting!	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simple language • Pilot branding / custom material • Highlight benefits for users • Be transparent
Address sufficiently user concerns	Involve, listen, discuss and reassure!
Keep users actively engaged	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share key outputs from project • Invite them to events - they can be your best promo!

